

LIS-Bibliometrics conference 2024- Exploring the Bibliometric Universe at the University of Brighton

Streamed live on Sep 12, 2024 DOI - [10.5281/zenodo.13832564](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13832564)

MAIN HALL

<https://youtube.com/live/nAbKhvqbktU>

Video Timings Session 1

[0:07:02](#) - Welcome to the conference - Professor Andrew Lloyd Acting Vice-Chancellor of the University of Brighton and Dr Barbara S. Lancho Barrantes Chair LIS Bibliometrics committee

[0:15:56](#) - Keynote - Professor Jennifer Byrne - A primer on research paper mills in biomedicine

[1:01:08](#) - Innovating Impact: Presenting AI-driven stories and visualised indicators - Dr Angela McGuire (Elsevier)

Session 2

[1:43:42](#) - Keynote - Professor Caroline Wagner - How bibliometrics inform decision making

[2:07:10](#) - Bibliometric methods for identifying AI-assisted papers - Andrew Gray

[2:45:36](#) - Making our metrics service less about metrics and more about service and support - Kate Lepage Session 3

[3:59:24](#) - Advanced Research Analytics: The Next Generation of OpenAlex- Jason Priem, CEO of OurResearch.

[4:34:17](#) - A pathway to impact: Unveiling the science behind patents and beyond - Dr. Ryan Beardsley (Clarivate)

[4:46:55](#) - A pathway to impact: Unveiling the science behind patents and beyond

[4:58:38](#) - Better living through bibliometrics: mapping scholars to government research priorities- Euan Adie, managing director of Overton

Session 4

[5:57:12](#) - Bibliometric and Research Impact Application Templates at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign Library. - William Mischo, Mary Schlembach

[6:29:48](#) - Navigating the Research Landscape : real-world examples of using Inspec Analytics to chart societal impact, government funding and industry-academia collaboration (IET) - Tim Aitkins, The IET

[6:57:47](#) - Keynote - Dr. Álvaro Cabezas Clavijo - Bibliometrics and Research Evaluation in Practice: Between Pragmatism and CoARA

[7:25:17](#) - Closing of Conference Dr Barbara S. Lancho Barrantes This event will capture the intersection between bibliometrics and prominent issues such as research integrity, AI, research culture, open research, and societal issues.

BREAKOUT ROOM

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xtv3q72fs_A

[0:00:00](#) - The meaning of scientific novelty: learning from expert reviews - Diogo Machado

[0:24:00](#) - Tips for CHIPS: Using thesaurus-based research analytics to train more employable engineering graduates - Tim Aitken and Katharine Hancox

[0:33:27](#) - Is Diversity of Expertise Correlated to Scientific Impact? An AI-Based Large-Scale Analysis in the Field of Computer Science Suggests so - Angelo Salatino

